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Composite of ionic liquid decorated cyclodextrin nanosponge, graphene oxide and chitosan: A novel catalyst support

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Abstract

A biocompatible hybrid system composed of graphene oxide (GO), chitosan (CS) and ionic liquid decorated cyclodextrin nanosponge (CDNS-IL) is synthesized and applied for the immobilization of Pd and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles to furnish a magnetic catalyst, Fe₃O₄/Pd@Hybrid. The justification for designing this hybrid system was benefiting from the capability of CDNS for formation of inclusion complex with substrates and acting as phase transfer agent. Moreover, IL itself could exert catalytic activity and improve anchoring Pd, while magnetic nanoparticles could render the catalyst easily separable. Moreover, the functional groups on CS could contribute to Pd anchoring. The catalytic activity of Fe₃O₄/Pd@Hybrid for promoting hydrogenation of nitro arenes and two coupling reactions in aqueous media was investigated. The results established that the catalyst could efficiently promote all the reactions under mild reaction condition. The investigation of the catalyst recyclability confirmed that the catalyst could be recycled for three reaction runs.

Keywords: Graphene oxide, Cyclodextrin Nanosponges, Chitosan